

第4讲 CiteSpace界面功能

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李杰科学网博客: <http://blog.sciencenet.cn/u/jerrycueb>

开放科学计量学学习平台: <https://www.metamatrix.cn/home>

The longer you can look back, the farther you can look forward (回顾历史越久远, 展望未来就越深远)。

导言

- 在前面CiteSpace下载和安装部分，我们已经接触了CiteSpace的功能参数区和可视化界面。这部分我们将重点介绍功能参数区的各种设置的具体含义以及可视化界面的功能。在CiteSpace中，功能参数区和可视化区域所承担的任务分工明确。
- 首先，CiteSpace的功能参数区承担了用户对所分析数据的详细参数设置，是数据分析的重要环节。可视化区域承担着数据结果的呈现，通常以知识网络的形式呈现所考察科学领域知识的结构与演化过程。
- 如果用基因编辑的例子作为对照，那么功能参数区就相当于在小孩未出生之前的基因编辑，这类似于在数据分析过程中对功能参数区参数的调整，可视化界面的结果相当于小孩出生之后的外在性状的表达。分析结果是否结构清晰，其本质是由数据决定的（也就是父母双方），参数调整（类似基因编辑）相当于初期的认为干预和控制，可视化界面的调整（类似与装扮）。可视化承担了最终结果的表达，但我们通过例子也很难或者，后期的可视化实际上仅仅是表达，其本质还取决于数据以及早期对分析数据参数的设置。
- 下面我们来认识CiteSpace功能参数区和可视化区域。

CiteSpace界面

- 在下载和安装CiteSpace后，首次联网运行，并会在最后自动打开CiteSpace界面（如右图）。此时，我们直接点击Agree即可进入功能参数区。

CiteSpace: Welcome!

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[6.4.R1 Demo Video](#) * [CiteSpace Survey](#) * [CiteSpace Blogs](#)

Current Versions: 6.4.R1, 6.3.R3, 6.3.R1 (Advanced)

[CiteSpace101 \(Experimental GPT\)](#) | [CiteSpace FAQ in English/Chinese \(英文/中文\)](#)

Videos: (1) [Visual Analytic Studies of Science \(2024\)](#) (2) [研究领域的形成, 发展, 和消亡 \(2022\)](#) (3) [Delineating the Scholarly Landscape of a Research Field \(2021\)](#)

Upgrade to CiteSpace (Advanced): [1 Year on 1 Computer](#); [2 Years on 2 Computers](#)

升级高级版: 微信/支付宝 (S/¥): [1年1台电脑](#); [2年2台电脑](#)

注意: CiteSpace的官网为 citespace.podia.com。任何其它网站均未经授权。

Warning: The citespace.podia.com is the official website of CiteSpace. CiteSpace distributed on any other websites are unauthorized.

System Information

CiteSpace 6.4.R1 (64-bit) Advanced	Windows 11 (null/null)	Java 22.0.2+11 (64-bit)
Built: December 27, 2024	Processors: 16	Substrate VM
Expire: December 31, 2026	Host: 67VGMJ3 159.226.100.236	Java Home: null

Key Publications

- Chen, C. (2020) [A Glimpse of the First Eight Months of the COVID-19 Literature on Microsoft Academic Graph](#). Front. Res. Metr. Anal. 5:607286.
- Chen, C., Song, M. (2019) [Visualizing a field of research: A methodology of systematic scientometric reviews](#). PLoS ONE, 14(10):e0223994.
- Chen, C. (2017) [Science mapping: A systematic review of the literature](#). JDIS, 2(2), 1-40.
- Chen, C. (2016) [CiteSpace: A Practical Guide for Mapping Scientific Literature](#). Nova Science Publishers.
- Chen, C. et al. (2010) [The structure and dynamics of co-citation clusters: A multiple-perspective co-citation analysis](#). JASIST, 61(7), 1386-1409.
- Chen, C. (2006) [CiteSpace II: Detecting and visualizing emerging trends and transient patterns in scientific literature](#). JASIST, 57(3), 359-377.
- Chen, C. (2004) [Searching for intellectual turning points: Progressive Knowledge Domain Visualization](#). Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci., 101(Suppl.), 5303-5310.
- Chen, C. (2010) [System and method for automatically generating systematic reviews of a scientific field](#). US Patent US20110295903A1.

Acknowledgements

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This version of Cite Space is for personal use only. Use it at your own risk.

功能参数区

- 右图为CiteSpace的功能参数区，主要包含了菜单栏和展开的参数设置区域。
- 菜单栏中包含了更加丰富的功能选项和参数设置。展开区域显示了最为核心的参数设置。
- 下面我们详细对各个区域参数名称及其功能进行性说明。

CiteSpace功能参数区概览

菜单栏

项目区

空间状态

过程报告

The screenshot displays the CiteSpace 6.4.R1 Advanced interface with the following sections:

- Web of Science**: Includes a Projects section with a dropdown menu (currently showing 'Demo 1: Terrorism (1996-2003)'), a 'New' button, and 'More Actions ...'. Below this are fields for 'Project Home', 'Data Directory', and 'Configuration' (Source=WoS; LRF=2.5; L/N=10; LBY=5; e=1.0). A 'Start' button is highlighted in green, along with 'Stop' and 'Reset' buttons. A 'JVM Memory' indicator shows 12887 (MB) Used and 0 %.
- Time Slicing**: A panel with 'From' (1996), 'To' (2003), and '#Years Per Slice' (1) dropdown menus.
- Text Processing**: A panel with 'Term Source' (checkboxes for Title, Abstract, Author Keywords (DE), Keywords Plus (ID)) and 'Term Type' (radio buttons for Noun Phrases, Burst Terms, Detect Bursts, Entropy).
- Node Types**: A panel with radio buttons for Author, Institution, Country, Keyword, Term, Source, Category, Reference (selected), Cited Author, and Cited Journal.
- Links**: A panel with 'Strength' (Cosine) and 'Scope' (Within Slices) dropdown menus.
- Selection Criteria**: A panel with tabs for g-index (selected), Top N, Top N%, Thresholds, Citations, Usage180, and Usage2013. It contains a text box with the formula $g^2 \leq k \sum_{i \leq g} c_i, k \in Z^+$ and a scale factor $k = 25$.
- Pruning**: A panel with tabs for Pruning and Visualization. Under Pruning, there are checkboxes for Pathfinder, Minimum Spanning Tree, Pruning sliced networks, and Pruning the merged network.

时间切片

文本处理

分析类型

关联强度

阈值设置

网络处理

CiteSpace功能参数区——新建项目

- 1 项目命名。
- 2 加载项目文件project.
- 3 加载数据文件data.
- 4 链接保留规模因子。
- 5 Look Back Years以施引文献发表时间为基准，来回溯分析参考文献时间。
- 6 每个节点允许的最大链接数。
- 7 设置所提取节点频次的最低值。

Time Slicing

From To #Years Per Slice

Text Processing

Term Source

Title Abstract Author Keywords (DE) Keywords Plus (ID)

Term Type

Noun Phrases Burst Terms

Node Types

Author Institution Country Keyword Term Source Category

Reference Cited Author Cited Journal

Links

Strength Scope

Selection Criteria

The selection uses a modified g-index in each slice: $g^2 \leq k \sum_{i \leq g} c_i, k \in Z^+$

To include more or fewer nodes, increase or decrease the scale factor k =

Pruning

Pruning

Pathfinder Pruning sliced networks

Minimum Spanning Tree Pruning the merged network

- 1 时间切片（Time Slicing）：具体含义是指对施引文献按照发文年份或者月份进行切分。所设置的时间区间必须在施引文献所发表年份的时间范围内。时间切片的数量用户可以根据自己的需求来进行设定。通常情况下设置的时间切片数量在7±2范围在可视化上或更优（个人看法）。
- 2 文本处理（Text Processing）：通过什么方式我们可以了解所下载的研究内容呢？CiteSpace提供了从施引文献标题、摘要以及关键词位置提取名词性术语的方法或直接提取关键词的方法来帮助用户了解所分析内容的主题。在节点类型的选择上则表现为，术语的提取需要选择Term，关键词则直接选择Keyword即可。注意Term分析需要经过Term type中noun phrase的处理过程。
- 3 分析类型（Node Types）：科学文献的元数据内容限定了我们可以进行分析的项目。例如，通过CiteSpace我们可以构建科学合作网络、科学研究主题网络、科学研究领域网络和共被引网络（文献、作者或期刊）。
- 4 相似性测度（Links）：存储在矩阵或者网络中的知识单元，其相似性的测度有多重方法。在大多数的分析中，Cosine（夹角余弦）是最常用的方法。因此，CiteSpace默认为Cosine的方法。
- 5 阈值设置（Selection Criteria）。也就是数据被纳入分析，必须满足一定的门槛。在门外的数据将不会纳入分析过程。这里默认使用g指数的方法来提取每一个时间切片中满足条件的施引文献，以进一步处理和分析。为了在分析中更加灵活，陈超美教授巧妙第引入了规模因子k，用户可以调整规模因子对分析结果进行调整。
- 6 网络调整（Pruning/Visualization）：这里共包含两个功能，一个是对网络的精简Pruning，一个是网络的显示处理。CiteSpace生成可视化结果是以网络的形式呈现，因此在一些情况下，网络密度过高，就像一个枝繁叶茂的大树一样，其结构很难显现出来。CiteSpace则提供了寻径网络和最小生成树的方法对网络进行剪裁。建议在默认情况下，用户不要去裁剪，应该结合初次得到的结果进行来判断。

运行案例

点击Start! 运行案例数据。并点击Visualize进入可视化界面。

Your Options

Project Title: Untitled

Time Frame: 1996-2003
Qualified Records: 1513

How do you like to proceed?

CiteSpace 6.4.R1 (64-bit) Advanced - (c) 2003-2024 Chaomei Chen - Home: C:\Users\metascience

File Projects Data Visualization Geographical Overlay Maps Analytics Network Text Preferences Tutorials Help

Web of Science

Projects: Demo 1: Terrorism (1996-2003)

Project Home: .:\citespace\Examples\WoS\Terrorism1990-2003\project

Data Directory: .:\citespace\Examples\WoS\Terrorism1990-2003\data

Configuration: Source=WoS; LRF=2.5; L/N=10; LB=5; e=1.0

JVM Memory 12887 (MB) Used 1 %

Space Status

1-year slices	criteria	space	nodes	links / all
Pruning configuration:				
1996	g=30, k=25	405	30	28 / 28
1997	g=41, k=25	561	41	87 / 87
1998	g=29, k=25	487	29	36 / 36
1999	g=54, k=25	766	54	135 / 243
2000	g=45, k=25	1025	45	112 / 195
2001	g=76, k=25	1590	76	190 / 768
2002	g=100, k=25	4986	100	250 / 967
2003	g=94, k=25	5064	94	235 / 426

Process Reports

Document Types
1513 Article

Distinct references [Valid]: 27660 95.5110%
Distinct references [Invalid]: 1300 4.4890%

Parsing Time: 1.169 seconds
Total Run time: 1.548 seconds

Merged network: Nodes=375, Links=1042
Exclusion List: 0

Time Slicing

From 1996 JAN To 2003 DEC #Years Per Slice 1

Text Processing

Term Source
 Title Abstract Author Keywords (DE) Keywords Plus (ID)

Term Type
 Noun Phrases Burst Terms

Node Types

Author Institution Country Keyword Term Source Category

Reference Cited Author Cited Journal

Links

Strength Cosine Scope Within Slices

Selection Criteria

The selection uses a modified g-index in each slice: $g^2 \leq k \sum_{i \leq g} c_i, k \in Z^+$

To include more or fewer nodes, increase or decrease the scale factor k = 25

Pruning Visualization

Pathfinder Pruning sliced networks
 Minimum Spanning Tree Pruning the merged network

CiteSpace 可视化界面

菜单栏

快捷工具

数据分析
基础参数

节点信息

可视化区域

控制面板

CiteSpace可视化界面

录屏 停止录屏 保存文件 保存PNG 保存SVG 运行数据 停止运行 背景颜色 黑色背景 白色背景 背景颜色 LSI算法 LLR算法 MI算法 用户自定义 GPT标签生成 LSI/LLR算法 聚类视图 圆形视图 圆形视图 时间线视图 时区视图 山峦视图 密度图

图形旋转 弧线连线 网络配色 网络聚类 SCI标签 CR标签 聚类趋势 聚类样式 统一样式 年轮样式

Spotlight Show/Hide Citation/Frequency Burst >>> <<< Search: ti:q1 | fu:* # clusters 87

引文或频次突显

时序共被引

信息检索

聚类总数

在初步运行的基础上，可视化网络相对稳定后，点击聚类。

The screenshot displays the CiteSpace software interface. On the left is a table of cited references. The main area shows a network visualization with nodes and edges. A purple callout box labeled '1' points to the 'Clustering' button in the toolbar. A dialog box titled 'All in One' is open, showing options for labeling clusters. A purple callout box labeled '5' points to the 'Source of Labels' dropdown menu in the dialog. A purple callout box labeled '网络的聚类' points to the network visualization. A purple callout box labeled '聚类标签的提取位置的选择' points to the 'Source of Labels' dropdown menu.

Visible	Count	Centra...	Year	Cited References
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	38	0.01	2001	SCHUSTER MA, 2001, NE...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	33	0.04	1997	FRANZ DR, 1997, JAMA-J...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	31	0.02	2002	GALEA S, 2002, NEW EN...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	30	0.10	1999	INGLESBY TV, 1999, JAMA...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	29	0.17	1999	HENDERSON DA, 1999, J...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	27	0.03	1999	HENDERSON DA, 1999, S...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	26	0.03	1997	TOROK TJ, 1997, JAMA-J...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	21	0.01	1999	NORTH CS, 1999, JAMA-J...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	17	0.04	1997	CHRISTOPHER GW, 1997...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	17	0.00	1998	HOFFMAN B, 1998, INSID...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	15	0.01	1997	TUCKER JB, 1997, JAMA...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	15	0.01	1997	SIMON JD, 1997, JAMA-J A...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	15	0.00	2002	SCHLENGER WE, 2002, J...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	13	0.13	1996	MALLONEE S, 1996, JAMA...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	12	0.01	2001	MELTZER MI, 2001, EMER...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	12	0.01	1999	ALIBEK K, 1999, BIOHAZA...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	12	0.03	2000	MACINTYRE AG, 2000, JA...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	12	0.02	1999	BRENNAN RJ, 1999, ANN ...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	12	0.06	1998	OKUMURA T, 1998, ACAD ...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	12	0.01	2000	INGLESBY TV, 2000, JAMA...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	12	0.01	1997	ZILINSKAS RA, 1997, JAM...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	11	0.01	1999	KEIM M, 1999, ANN EMER...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	11	0.01	1997	KAUFMANN AF, 1997, EM...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	10	0.10	1999	PFEFFERBAUM B, 1999, A...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	10	0.01	2001	WETTER DC, 2001, AM J ...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	9	0.04	1999	*CDCP, 1999, MMWR-MO...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	9	0.00	2001	WAECKERLE JF, 2001, A...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	9	0.02	1997	HOLLOWAY HC, 1997, JA...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	9	0.00	1997	KOLAVIC SA, 1997, JAMA...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	8	0.01	1999	DIXON TC, 1999, NEW EN...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	8	0.00	2002	INGLESBY TV, 2002, JAMA...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	8	0.07	2001	JERNIGAN JA, 2001, EME...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	8	0.01	1998	CARTER A, 1998, FOREIG...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	8	0.03	2001	ARNON SS, 2001, JAMA-J...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	7	0.00	1996	OKUMURA T, 1996, ANN ...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	7	0.01	2002	YEHUDA R, 2002, NEW E...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	7	0.06	2002	BREMAN JG, 2002, NEW ...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	7	0.00	2002	KAPLAN EH, 2002, P NAT...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	7	0.00	2000	KHAN AS, 2000, LANCET...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	7	0.04	1998	OKUMURA T, 1998, ACAD...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	7	0.00	1999	KORTEPETER MG, 1999, ...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	7	0.00	2001	DENNIS DT, 2001, JAMA-J...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	7	0.01	1999	RICHARDS CF, 1999, AN...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	6	0.00	1999	OTOOLE T, 1999, EMERG...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	6	0.00	2001	INGLESBY TV, 2001, CLIN...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	6	0.00	2000	*CDCP, 2000, MMWR-MO...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	6	0.00	1999	TERR LC, 1999, AM J PSY...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	6	0.02	2001	BARBERA J, 2001, JAMA-J...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	6	0.00	2002	SILVER RC, 2002, JAMA-J...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	6	0.00	2002	ROTZ LD, 2002, EMERG I...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	6	0.01	1998	SHARP TW, 1998, ANN E...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	6	0.06	1994	*AM PSYCH ASS, 1994, DI...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	6	0.04	1999	HARVEY AG, 1999, J CON...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	6	0.02	2000	PFEFFERBAUM B, 2000, ...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	5	0.00	2001	ARQUILLA J, 2001, NETW...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	5	0.00	1999	PFEFFERBAUM B, 1999, I...

网络的聚类

5

聚类标签的提取位置的选择

All in One

Choose one of the following sources to label clusters:

- T: Title words from citing articles
- R: Title words from cited references (Require Scopus or Dimension)
- K: Keywords (WoS: since 1990)
- S: Subject Categories

Source of Labels

OK Cancel

1997

SCHUSTER MA (2001)

GALEA S (2002)

聚类结果

可视化区域

• 该区域的核心任务是来可视化所分析的结果，并查询所分析的结果。

• 核心功能：

- 1. 可视化调整。
- 2. 结果查询。

可视化调整 (网络布局样式)

1 网络视图

2 时间线视图

3 时区图

可视化调整 (网络布局样式)

可视化调整（网络布局样式-密度图）

可视化调整

• 按照元素思考？可以调整可视化结果上的哪些元素？标签（大小、颜色、样式）、节点（大小、颜色、样式）、连线（宽窄、颜色）……画布的颜色、网络的整体配色等等。

• 整体显示配置：菜单栏display和快捷工具栏

可视化调整

网络连线调整

The screenshot shows the CiteSpace software interface with the 'Links' panel open. The 'Link Shape' section has 'Straightline' selected. The 'Link Width' is set to 'Uniformed/Weighted'. The 'Link Color' section includes options for 'Solid Lines: Set Color' (Ctrl-B), 'Dashed Lines: Set Color' (Ctrl-5), and 'Link Transparency: 0.0 - 1.0'. There are also options for 'Preset Single-Colored Link Styles' (Yellow-Green Links (Black), Yellow-Brown Links (White), Restore Multi-colored Links), 'Solid Lines: Show/Hide' (Ctrl-F11), 'Dashed Lines: Show/Hide' (Ctrl-F11), 'Link Labels: Show/Hide', 'Link Raw Count: Show/Hide', and 'Link Strengths: Show/Hide'. The main visualization area shows a network graph with nodes and links, and a list of nodes on the left.

Visible	Count	Centra...	Year	Cit
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	38	0.01	2001	SCHUS
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	33	0.04	1997	FRANZ
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	31	0.02	2002	GALEA
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	30	0.10	1999	INGLES
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	29	0.17	1999	HENDE
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	27	0.03	1999	HENDE
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	26	0.03	1997	TOROK
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	21	0.01	1999	NORTH
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	17	0.04	1997	CHRIST
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	17	0.00	1998	HOFFMA
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	15	0.01	1997	TUCKER
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	15	0.01	1997	SIMON J
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	15	0.00	2002	SCHLEN
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	13	0.13	1996	MALLON
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	12	0.01	2001	MELTZE
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	12	0.01	1999	ALIBEK
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	12	0.03	2000	MACINT
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	12	0.02	1999	BRENNAN
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	12	0.06	1998	OKUMURA
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	12	0.01	2000	INGLESBY
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	12	0.01	1997	ZILINSKAS
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	11	0.01	1999	KEIM M.
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	11	0.01	1997	KAUFMANN
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	10	0.10	1999	PFEFFERBAUM
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	10	0.01	2001	WETTER DC
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	9	0.04	1999	*CDCP, 1999
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	9	0.00	2001	WAECKERLE
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	9	0.02	1997	HOLLOWAY
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	9	0.00	1997	KOLAVIC
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	8	0.01	1999	DIXON TC
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	8	0.00	2002	INGLESBY TV
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	8	0.07	2001	JERNIGAN
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	8	0.01	1998	CARTER A
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	8	0.03	2001	ARNON SS
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	7	0.00	1996	OKUMURA T
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	7	0.01	2002	YEHUDA R
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	7	0.06	2002	BREMAN JG
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	7	0.00	2000	KAPLAN EH
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	7	0.00	2000	KHAN AS
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	7	0.04	1998	OKUMURA T
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	7	0.00	1999	KORTEPETER
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	7	0.00	2001	DENNIS DT
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	7	0.01	1999	RICHARDS CF
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	6	0.00	1999	OTOOLE T
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	6	0.00	2001	INGLESBY TV
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	6	0.00	2000	*CDCP, 2000
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	6	0.00	1999	TERR LC
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	6	0.02	2001	BARBERA J
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	6	0.00	2002	SILVER RC
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	6	0.00	2002	ROTZ LD
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	6	0.01	1998	SHARP TW
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	6	0.06	1994	*AM PSYCH ASS
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	6	0.04	1999	HARVEY AG
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	6	0.02	2000	PFEFFERBAUM B
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	5	0.00	2001	ARQUILLA J
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	5	0.00	1999	PFEFFERBAUM B

网络节点标签调整

The screenshot shows the CiteSpace software interface with the 'Labels' panel open. The 'Label Alignment' section has 'R MI USR GPT' buttons. The 'Label Boxes' section has 'Label Color' and 'Label Background Color' options. The 'Label Font Size' and 'Label Position' sections have 'Spotlight' and 'Show/Hide Citation' buttons. The 'Overlay Labels: Show/Hide' section has a 'Ctrl-O' button. The 'Change Labels: Create an Alias Template' section has a 'Timeline View' button. The 'Predefined Label Color Styles' section has 'White Background: Cluster Labels: Black; Node Labels: Gray' and 'Black Background: Cluster Labels: White; Node Labels: Gray' options. The main visualization area shows a network graph with nodes and links, and a list of nodes on the left.

Visible	Count	Centra...	Year	Cited Refer
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	38	0.01	2001	SCHUSTER MA
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	33	0.04	1997	FRANZ DR, 199
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	31	0.02	2002	GALEA S, 2002,
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	30	0.10	1999	INGLESBY TV, 1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	29	0.17	1999	HENDERSON D
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	27	0.03	1999	HENDERSON D
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	26	0.03	1997	TOROK TJ, 1997
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	21	0.01	1999	NORTH CS, 199
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	17	0.04	1997	CHRISTOPHER
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	17	0.00	1998	HOFFMAN B, 19
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	15	0.01	1997	TUCKER JB, 19
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	15	0.01	1997	SIMON JD, 1997
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	15	0.00	2002	SCHLENGER W, 2002, S...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	13	0.13	1996	MALLONEE S, 1996, JAMA...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	12	0.01	2001	MELTZER MI, 2001, EMER...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	12	0.01	1999	ALIBEK K, 1999, BIOHAZA...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	12	0.03	2000	MACINTYRE AG, 2000, JA...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	12	0.02	1999	BRENNAN RJ, 1999, ANN ...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	12	0.06	1998	OKUMURA T, 1998, ACAD ...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	12	0.01	2000	INGLESBY TV, 2000, JAMA...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	12	0.01	1997	ZILINSKAS RA, 1997, JAM...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	11	0.01	1999	KEIM M, 1999, ANN EMER...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	11	0.01	1997	KAUFMANN AF, 1997, EM...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	10	0.10	1999	PFEFFERBAUM B, 1999, A...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	10	0.01	2001	WETTER DC, 2001, AM J ...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	9	0.04	1999	*CDCP, 1999, MMWR-MO...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	9	0.00	2001	WAECKERLE JF, 2001, A...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	9	0.02	1997	HOLLOWAY HC, 1997, JA...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	9	0.00	1997	KOLAVIC SA, 1997, JAMA...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	9	0.00	1999	DIXON TC, 1999, NEW EN...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	8	0.01	2000	INGLESBY TV, 2000, JAMA...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	8	0.01	1997	ZILINSKAS RA, 1997, JAM...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	8	0.01	1999	KEIM M, 1999, ANN EMER...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	8	0.01	1997	KAUFMANN AF, 1997, EM...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	10	0.10	1999	PFEFFERBAUM B, 1999, A...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	10	0.01	2001	WETTER DC, 2001, AM J ...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	9	0.04	1999	*CDCP, 1999, MMWR-MO...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	9	0.00	2001	WAECKERLE JF, 2001, A...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	9	0.02	1997	HOLLOWAY HC, 1997, JA...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	9	0.00	1997	KOLAVIC SA, 1997, JAMA...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	8	0.01	1999	DIXON TC, 1999, NEW EN...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	8	0.00	2002	INGLESBY TV, 2002, JAMA...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	8	0.07	2001	JERNIGAN JA, 2001, EME...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	8	0.01	1998	CARTER A, 1998, FOREIG...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	8	0.03	2001	ARNON SS, 2001, JAMA-J ...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	7	0.00	1996	OKUMURA T, 1996, ANN ...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	7	0.01	2002	YEHUDA R, 2002, NEW E...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	7	0.06	2002	BREMAN JG, 2002, NEW ...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	7	0.00	2002	KAPLAN EH, 2002, P NAT...

控制面板:节点、标签的微调功能区;图形元素颜色的快速设置;突发性探测的设置区域;时间线视图的调整。。

1 对terms和关键词标签大小、节点大小和显示数量的调整。

2 对其他类型节点大小、标签大小以及显示数量的调整。

3 对聚类标签大小和数量调整;对聚类标签显示长度的控制。

4 聚类标签和节点标签的防覆盖。

1 图形整体颜色的配置。

2 图形元素透明度的调整。

控制面板:节点、标签的微调功能区;图形元素颜色的快速设置;突发性探测的设置区域;时间线视图的调整。。

1 突发性探测参数设置。
通常默认即可。

刷新与查看

控制面板:节点、标签的微调功能区;图形元素颜色的快速设置;突发性探测的设置区域;时间线视图的调整。。

Control Panel

Colormap Burstness Search Clusters

Labels Layout Views

Fisheye View

Distortion

Focal Point

Timeline View Controls

Cluster Label Padding

SubCluster Label Height

Row Span

Link Filter

Snap Node Positions

Clusters	Uniform	Tree Rings
Centrality	Sigma	Eigenvector
WoS TC	WoS U180	WoS U2013

1 时间线视图调整

从CiteSpace概念模型维度认识分析结果。

CiteSpace中的概念模型

The screenshot shows the CiteSpace software interface. The main window displays a list of cited references with columns for Visible, Count, Centrality, Year, and Cited References. The sidebar menu includes options for Clusters, Visual Encoding, Cluster Labels, Layout Optimization, Cluster Exploration, Level of Detail, and Expectation Maximization. A red circle highlights the 'Cluster Explorer' option in the sidebar.

Visible	Count	Centra...	Year	Cited References
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	38	0.01	2001	SCHUSTER MA, 2001, NE
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	33	0.04	1997	FRANZ DR, 1997, JAMA-J
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	31	0.02	2002	GALEA S, 2002, NEW EN
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	30	0.10	1999	INGLESBY TV, 1999, JAM
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	29	0.17	1999	HENDERSON DA, 1999, J
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	27	0.03	1999	HENDERSON DA, 1999, J
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	26	0.03	1997	TOROK TJ, 1997, JAMA-J
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	21	0.01	1999	NORTH CS, 1999, JAMA-J
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	17	0.04	1997	CHRISTOPHER GW, 1997
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	17	0.00	1998	HOFFMAN B, 1998, INSID
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	15	0.01	1997	TUCKER JB, 1997, JAMA-J
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	15	0.01	1997	SIMON JD, 1997, JAMA-J
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	15	0.00	2002	SCHLENGER WE, 2002, J
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	13	0.13	1996	MALLONEE S, 1996, JAM
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	12	0.01	2001	MELTZER MI, 2001, EMER
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	12	0.01	1999	ALIBEK K, 1999, BIOHAZ
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	12	0.03	2000	MACINTYRE AG, 2000, JA
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	12	0.02	1999	BRENNAN RJ, 1999, ANN
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	12	0.06	1998	OKUMURA T, 1998, ACAD
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	12	0.01	2000	INGLESBY TV, 2000, JAM
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	12	0.01	1997	ZILINSKAS RA, 1997, JAM
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	11	0.01	1999	KEIM M, 1999, ANN EMER
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	11	0.01	1997	KAUFMANN AF, 1997, EM
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	10	0.10	1999	PFEFFERBAUM B, 1999, J
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	10	0.01	2001	WETTER DC, 2001, AM J
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	9	0.04	1999	*CDCP, 1999, MMWR-MO
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	9	0.00	2001	WAECKERLE JF, 2001, A
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	9	0.02	1997	HOLLOWAY HC, 1997, JA
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	9	0.00	1997	KOLAVIC SA, 1997, JAMA-J
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	8	0.01	1999	DIXON TC, 1999, NEW EN
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	8	0.00	2002	INGLESBY TV, 2002, JAM
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	8	0.07	2001	JERNIGAN JA, 2001, EME
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	8	0.01	1998	CARTER A, 1998, FOREIC
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	8	0.03	2001	ARNON SS, 2001, JAMA-J
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	7	0.00	1996	OKUMURA T, 1996, ANN
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	7	0.01	2002	YEHUDA R, 2002, NEW E
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	7	0.06	2002	BREMAN JG, 2002, NEW
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	7	0.00	2002	KAPLAN EH, 2002, P NAT
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	7	0.00	2000	KHAN AS, 2000, LANCET
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	7	0.04	1998	OKUMURA T, 1998, ACAD
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	7	0.00	1999	KORTEPETER MG, 1999,
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	7	0.00	2001	DENNIS DT, 2001, JAMA-J
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	7	0.01	1999	RICHARDS CF, 1999, AN
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	6	0.00	1999	OTOOLE T, 1999, EMERG
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	6	0.00	2001	INGLESBY TV, 2001, CLIN
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	6	0.00	2000	*CDCP, 2000, MMWR-MO
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	6	0.00	1999	TERR LC, 1999, AM J PSY
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	6	0.02	2001	BARBERA J, 2001, JAMA-J
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	6	0.00	2002	SILVER RC, 2002, JAMA-J
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	6	0.00	2002	ROTZ LD, 2002, EMERG I
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	6	0.01	1998	SHARP TW, 1998, ANN E...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	6	0.06	1994	*AM PSYCH ASS, 1994, DI...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	6	0.04	1999	HARVEY AG, 1999, J CON...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	6	0.02	2000	PFEFFERBAUM B, 2000,

Looking for Saved Information of Clusters

Can you locate the clusters folder where the required information of clusters is saved?

Yes No Cancel

Open

Look In: project

Folder name: C:\Users\metascience\citespace\Examples\Template\project

Files of Type: All Files

Open Cancel

这里显示了CiteSpace概念模型中的元素

思考：CiteSpace概念图上的核心元素是如何与右侧图上的内容对应的？

CiteSpace: Cluster Explorer

Select	Cluster ID	Size	Silhouette	mean(Year)	Top Terms (LSI)	Top Terms (log-likelihood ratio, p-level)	Terms (mutual information)
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	0	43	0.973	2000	nationwide longitudinal study; child exposure; s...	terrorist attack (116.74, 1.0E-4); 11th terrorist att...	psychological sequelae (1.43); new york (1.43); ...
<input type="checkbox"/>	1	38	0.826	2000	terrorist attack; bioterrorism preparedness iii; bi...	bacterial pathogen (46.03, 1.0E-4); catastrophe...	anthrax terrorism (0.8); family physician prefer...
<input type="checkbox"/>	2	35	0.914	1997	executive summary; following bioterrorism expo...	terrorist attack (30.58, 1.0E-4); emergency physi...	bioterrorism (0.96); biowarfare (0.96); threat (0...
<input type="checkbox"/>	3	33	0.851	1998	major incident; biological terrorism; convention...	medical services system (34.74, 1.0E-4); hospita...	protective equipment (0.53); health care facility ...
<input type="checkbox"/>	4	32	0.822	1999	future challenge; smallpox-vaccination policy; m...	case isolation (44.53, 1.0E-4); geographical spr...	threat preparation (0.61); medical response (0...
<input type="checkbox"/>	5	24	0.961	1994	psychological aspect; chemical defense; surgic...	eye injury (37.9, 1.0E-4); terrorist bombing (37.9...	chemical defense (0.15); psychological aspect (...
<input type="checkbox"/>	6	19	0.936	1998	battery-powered notebook; thermal cyclor; dom...	bioterrorism preparedness (35.25, 1.0E-4); do...	grand strategy strategy (0.05); bioterrorism (0.0...
<input type="checkbox"/>	7	12	0.912	1996	water supplies; chemical terrorism; involving ch...	olympic game (22.4, 1.0E-4); terrorist incident (2...	water supplies (0.03); bioterrorism (0.02); chem...

Coverage	GCS	LCS	Bibliography
12	0	0	GALEA, S (2003-JAN) Trends of probable post-traumatic stress disorder in new york city after the september 11 terrorist attacks. AMERICAN JOURNAL OF EPIDEMIOLOGY, V158, P11
9	0	0	KARAM, E (2003-JAN) Psychosocial consequences of war among civilian populations. CURRENT OPINION IN PSYCHIATRY
8	0	0	FORD, CA (2003-JAN) Reactions of young adults to september 11, 2001. ARCHIVES OF PEDIATRICS & ADOLESCENT MEDICINE
7	0	0	ROSENHECK, R (2003-JAN) Use of mental health services by veterans with ptsd after the terrorist attacks of september 11. AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PSYCHIATRY
7	7	0	GALEA, S (2002-JAN) Posttraumatic stress disorder in manhattan, new york city, after the september 11th terrorist attacks. JOURNAL OF URBAN HEALTH-BULLETIN OF THE NEW YORK ACADEMY OF MEDICINE, V79, P14
7	34	0	SCHLENGER, WE (2002-JAN) Psychological reactions to terrorist attacks - findings from the national study of americans' reactions to september 11. JAMA-JOURNAL OF THE AMERICAN MEDICAL ASSOCIATION
7	1	0	SHAW, JA (2003-JAN) Children exposed to war/terrorism. CLINICAL CHILD AND FAMILY PSYCHOLOGY REVIEW
7	2	0	LEE, A (2002-JAN) Post-traumatic stress disorder and terrorism. CURRENT OPINION IN PSYCHIATRY
7	0	0	FAIRBROTHER, G (2003-JAN) Posttraumatic stress reactions in new york city children after the september 11, 2001, terrorist attacks. AMBULATORY PEDIATRICS
6	0	0	MARSHALL, RD (2003-JAN) Contextualizing trauma: using evidence-based treatments in a multicultural community after 9/11. PSYCHIATRIC QUARTERLY, V74, P20

Freq	Burst	BurstB...	BurstE...	Degree	Centra...	Σ	PageR...	Label	Author	Year	Title	Source	Vol	Page	HalfLife	DOI	Cluster
3	0.00			4.000	1.00	0.00	0.00	SHAH	SHAH B	1997	...	SUDAA...	V0	P0	4.5		0
3	0.00			10.00	1.00	0.00	0.00	WEISS	WEISS	1997	...	ASSESS...	V0	P399	4.5		0
2	0.00			2.000	1.00	0.00	0.00	ASUKA	ASUKA	2002	...	J NER...	V190	P175	0.5		0
2	0.00			8.003	1.00	0.00	0.00	BAKER	BAKE	2002	...	J AM M...	V57	P117	0.5		0
3	0.00			11.004	1.00	0.00	0.00	AHER	AHER	2002	...	PSYC...	V65	P289	0.5		0
2	0.00			8.003	1.00	0.00	0.00	BAKER	BAKE	2002	...	J AM M...	V57	P121	0.5		0
3	0.00			2.000	1.00	0.00	0.00	NORRI	NORRI	2001	...	50000...	V0	P0	0.5		0
2	0.00			3.000	1.00	0.00	0.00	BAREL	BAREL	2002	...	INJ PR...	V8	P91	0.5		0
4	0.00			4.000	1.00	0.00	0.00	VLAHO	VLAHO	2002	...	AM J E...	V155	P988	0.5		0
3	0.00			3.000	1.00	0.00	0.00	POLE	POLE N	2001	...	J NER...	V189	P442	0.5		0
7	0.00			12.001	1.00	0.00	0.00	YEHU	YEHU	2002	...	NEW E...	V346	P108	-0.5		0
3	0.00			3.001	1.00	0.00	0.00	SHIN L	SHIN LM	1999	...	AM J P...	V156	P575	3.5		0
2	0.00			8.000	1.00	0.00	0.00	*US B...	*US B...	2000	...	CENS...	V0	P0	2.5		0
4	0.00			9.002	1.00	0.00	0.00	NORT...	NORT...	2002	...	JAMA-J...	V288	P633	0.5		0
6	0.00			3.000	1.00	0.00	0.00	TERR...	TERR...	1999	...	AM J P...	V156	P1536	2.5		0
5	0.00			4.000	1.00	0.00	0.00	PFEFF...	PFEFF...	1999	...	J AM A...	V38	P1372	3.5		0
10	0.00			11.010	1.00	0.00	0.00	PFEFF...	PFEFF...	1999	...	AM J P...	V156	P1069	2.5		0
6	0.00			7.000	1.00	0.00	0.00	SILV...	SILV...	2002	...	JAMA-J...	V288	P1235	0.5		0
2	0.00			11.004	1.00	0.00	0.00	ALLW...	ALLW...	2002	...	J AM A...	V41	P450	0.5		0
2	0.00			4.001	1.00	0.00	0.00	BRESL...	BRESL...	1997	...	ARCH...	V54	P81	4.5		0
4	0.00			9.000	1.00	0.00	0.00	SHALE	SHALE	1998	...	AM J P...	V155	P630	4.5		0
21	0.00			9.001	1.00	0.00	0.00	NORT...	NORT...	1999	...	JAMA-J...	V282	P755	2.5		0
31	0.00			14.002	1.00	0.00	0.00	GALEA	GALEA	2002	...	NEW E...	V346	P982	0.5		0
2	0.00			3.000	1.00	0.00	0.00	BRESL...	BRESL...	1997	...	ARCH...	V54	P1044	4.5		0
3	0.00			1.000	1.00	0.00	0.00	TUCK...	TUCK...	2000	...	J BEH...	V27	P406	1.5		0
3	0.00			2.001	1.00	0.00	0.00	PREZA	PREZA	2002	...	NEW E...	V347	P806	0.5		0
3	0.00			4.000	1.00	0.00	0.00	PFEFF...	PFEFF...	2001	...	PSYC...	V64	P202	0.5		0
38	0.00			13.001	1.00	0.00	0.00	SCHU...	SCHU...	2001	...	NEW E...	V345	P1507	1.5		0

Summary Sentences

Representative Sentences

Selection method:

- Centrality
- PageRank
- select from Abstracts

Start

Clusters processed: 0 of 6

Time taken (sec): 21.893

Timeout

Save the List

可视化图中的概念模型呈现

思考：CiteSpace概念图上的核心元素是如何与左侧图上的内容对应的？

其他-特定时间的共被引连线

其他-单节点信息的查询

CiteSpace: Display Merged - (c) 2003-2024 Chaomei Chen - Project Home: C:\Users\metascience\.citespace\Examples\WoS\Terrorism1990-2003\project

File Data Visualization Display Nodes Links Labels Clusters Overlays Filters Summary Export Windows Help

Visible Count Centra... Year Cited References

Visible	Count	Centra...	Year	Cited References
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	38	0.01	2001	SCHUSTER MA, 2001, NE...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	33	0.04	1997	FRANZ DR, 1997, JAMA-J...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	31	0.02	2002	GALEA S, 2002, NEW EN...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	30	0.10	1999	INGLESBY TV, 1999, JAMA...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	29	0.17	1999	HENDERSON DA, 1999, J...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	27	0.03	1999	HENDERSON DA, 1999, S...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	26	0.03	1997	TOROK TJ, 1997, JAMA-J...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	21	0.01	1999	NORTH CS, 1999, JAMA-J...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	17	0.04	1997	CHRISTOPHER GW, 1997...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	17	0.00	1998	HOFFMAN B, 1998, INSID...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	15	0.01	1997	TUCKER JB, 1997, JAMA...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	15	0.01	1997	SIMON JD, 1997, JAMA-J...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	15	0.00	2002	SCHLENGER WE, 2002, J...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	13	0.13	1996	MALLONEE S, 1996, JAMA...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	12	0.01	2001	MELTZER MI, 2001, EMER...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	12	0.01	1999	ALIBEK K, 1999, BIOHAZA...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	12	0.03	2000	MACINTYRE AG, 2000, JA...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	12	0.02	1999	BRENNAN RJ, 1999, ANN...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	12	0.06	1998	OKUMURA T, 1998, ACAD...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	12	0.01	2000	INGLESBY TV, 2000, JAMA...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	12	0.01	1997	ZILINSKAS RA, 1997, JAM...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	11	0.01	1999	KEIM M, 1999, ANN EMER...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	11	0.01	1997	KAUFMANN AF, 1997, EM...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	10	0.10	1999	PFEFFERBAUM B, 1999, A...
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 December 30, 2024, 1:50:15 PM CST
 WoS: C:\Users\metascience\.citespace\Examples\WoS\Terrorism1990-2003\data
 Timespan: 1996-2003 (Slice Length=1)
 Selection Criteria: g-index (k=25), LRF=2.5, L/N=10, LBY=5, e=1.0
 Network: N=375, E=1042 (Density=0.0149)
 Largest 1 CCs: 236 (62%)
 Nodes Labeled: 1.0%
 Pruning: None
 Modularity Q=0.6917
 Weighted Mean Silhouette S=0.8958
 Harmonic Mean(Q, S)=0.7806

#6 bioterrorism preparedness
 #7 olympic game
 #4 car...
 #2 emergency physician system
 #1 bacterial pathogen
 #5 eye injury
 #0 terrorist attack

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 Concept Tree (Citation Context)
 Pennant Diagram
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 Clear the Label
 Bookmark the Node
 Clear the Bookmark
 Annotate the Node
 Clear the Annotation
 Go to URL
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 The Lens
 Google Scholar
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 ACM DL
 Supreme Court
 CiteSeer
 List Cluster Members
 List Citing Papers to the Cluster
 Draw Similarity Networks (LSA)
 Hide Node
 Hide Cluster
 Restore Hidden Nodes
 Add to the Exclusion List
 Clear the Exclusion List
 Add to the Alias List (Primary)
 Add to the Alias List (Secondary)

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